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PREPARATION, CHARACTERIZATION OF PULSATILE MICROSPHERES DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVE AGENT

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The aim of present study was to formulate and evaluate the Quinapril Hydrochloride loaded pulsatile microspheres by solvent evaporation technique. **Method:** Ethyl cellulose and Eudragit Rs 100 are biocompatible polymer is used as the retardant material. The effects of process conditions such as drug loading, polymer type and solvent type on the characteristics of microspheres were investigated. **Results:** The prepared microspheres were characterized for their particle size, drug loading and drug release. The in-vitro release studies were carried out in pH 1.2, phosphate buffer at pH 6.8 and pH 7.4. The prepared microspheres were white, free flowing and spherical in shape. The drug-loaded microspheres showed 89.30% of entrapment with particle size 235.2 μ m and the in-vitro release studies showed that Quinapril Hydrochloride microspheres of 85.14%. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that, the prepared microspheres formulation showed compliance with chronotherapeutic objective of hypertension.

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INTRODUCTION

Pulsatile drug delivery systems are characterized by at least two distinctive drug release phases following a predetermined lag time. Drug's release may be controlled by time, by site or a combination of the two parameters.[1-5] A delayed release delivery system (where time controls the release) would meet the needs of chronopathologies with symptoms mostly recurring at night time or in the early morning whereas site-specific delivery in to the colon might enable an improvement in the treatment. In time controlled delivery systems, the release profile is determined by formulation parameters while in site specific controlled delivery systems the release profile is determined by parameters related to gastrointestinal environment.[6,7] Time controlled systems are divided into those using barrier technologies around the active agent designed to degrade or dissolve after a certain time, and in those that the degradation of the polymer itself induces the release of the active agent.

The solvent evaporation is simple method enables the entrapment of a wide range of hydrophobic drugs [8]. Ethyl cellulose is non-biodegradable, bio-compatible, non-toxic natural polymer and widely used in oral and topical formulation. [9,10]

The main objective of this work was to investigate the possibility of obtaining a pulsatile release formulation of Quinapril hydrochloride microspheres by using Ethyl cellulose and Eudragit rs100 in drug with various polymer ratios. The various physicochemical characteristics and the *in-vitro* release rates from these microspheres were thus examined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Quinapril Hydrochloride was purchased from Ozone Lab. Mumbai, India. Ethyl cellulose from S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Mumbai and Eudragit Rs 100 purchased from Yarrow chem. Products Mumbai. Dichloromethane was purchased from LOBA chem. Mumbai. All other reagents used in the study were of analytical grade and were used as received.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

This is the method widely used in the microencapsulation process. Calculated quantity of polymer was dissolved in Dichloromethane (10ml) to form a homogenous polymer solution.[11] Then calculated quantity of drug was added to the polymer solution and mixed thoroughly. The resulting mixture was then added in a thin stream of 300ml of aqueous solution containing 0.4% PVA solution while stirring at 500rpm to emulsify the added dispersion as fine droplets. The solvent, dichloromethane was then removed by evaporation during continuous stirring at room temperature for 3 hours to produce spherical microspheres. Here dichloromethane was used as polymer solvent, aqueous solution as the microencapsulating vehicle. During 3hours stirring period, dichloromethane was completely removed by evaporation [12-13]. The microspheres were collected by vacuum filtration and washed repeatedly and dried in room temperature over a night to get free flowing microspheres. The composition of formulation is given in table (1)

EVALUATION OF MICROSPHERES ^[10-15]

Drug-Polymer interaction Study

Interaction between drug-polymer was studied by Infra Red spectroscopy using FTIR spectrometer. Sample preparation involved mixing the sample with potassium bromide (KBr), triturating in glass mortar and finally placing in the sample holder. The spectrum was scanned over a frequency range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Particle Size Analysis

The size was measured using an optical microscope and the mean particle size was calculated by measuring 100 particles with the help of a calibrated ocular micrometer.

Drug content

10mg drug loaded microspheres were dissolved in a small quantity of methanol and the volume was made up to 100ml with phosphate buffer pH 7.4. It was stirred for 12hrs. After stirring the solution was filtered through whatman filter paper and the absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 210nm after suitable dilution

Drug loading capacity

Drug loading capacity was calculated by:

$$\text{Drug loading (\%)} = \frac{\text{M actual}}{\text{weighed quantity of powder of microspheres}} \times 100$$

Where M actual is the actual drug content in weighed quantity of powder of microspheres

Percentage yield

The prepared microspheres were collected and weighed. The yield was calculated by dividing the measured weight by the total weight of all non volatile components. The percentage yield of microspheres was calculated as follows.

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of microsphere}}{\text{Theoretical weight of drug and polymer}} \times 100$$

Scanning Electron Microscopy

The samples were dried thoroughly in vacuum desiccators before mounting on brass specimen studies. The samples were mounted on specimen studies using double sided carbon adhesive tape, and gold alloy of 120A° knees was coated on the sample using sputter coating unit in Argon ambient of 8 – 10 Pascal with plasma voltage about 10mA. The sputtering was done for nearly 10 sec to obtain uniform coating on the sample to enable good quality SEM images. The SEM was operated at low accelerating voltage of about 10mA. The gold coated sample placed in chamber of SEM (Jeol, JSM 6390 LA) and secondary images were recorded.

In-vitro dissolution study:

Dissolution studies were carried out using USP II dissolution test apparatus (paddle). Capsule was tied to paddle with a cotton thread so that the capsule was immersed completely in dissolution media but not float. In order to simulate the pH changes along the GI tract, three dissolution media with pH 1.2, 7.4 and 6.8 were sequentially used, (sequential pH change method). The pH 1.2 was first used for 2 hrs then removed and the fresh phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was added. After 4 hrs the medium was removed and colonic fluid phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was added for subsequent study. 900 ml of the dissolution medium was used at each time. Rotation speed was 50 rpm and temperature was maintained at $37\pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$. 10ml of dissolution medium was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals and fresh dissolution media was replaced. The withdrawn samples were analyzed at 210 nm, by UV absorption spectroscopy and the cumulative percentage release was calculated.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Pulsatile microspheres of Quinapril Hydrochloride were developed to prolong the gastric residence time and to increase the drug bioavailability. Quinapril Hydrochloride was chosen as a model drug because it is better absorbed in the stomach than the lower gastro intestinal tract.

Drug-exipients compatibility

FTIR:

IR spectra for drug and optimized formulation (Fig.No.1 & 2) revealed that there was no incompatibility between drug and excipients because of no change in the wave numbers of functional groups of Quinapril Hydrochloride.

Percentage yield

The percentage yield of three formulations was ranging from 77.11 to 84.34 respectively (Table 2). This higher percentage yields indicates that this method was very useful for adoption in the formulation of Quinapril Hydrochloride microsphere.

Drug loading and encapsulation efficiency

The results of the variation in drug loading and encapsulation efficiency with polymers ratio is shown in (table 2). Higher percentage of loading was obtained in F4 was 96.95% with respect to ethyl cellulose. The encapsulation process was found to be good and 89.30 to 96.95% of the drug employed in the process was encapsulated by the microsphere.

Particle size

The particle size of Quinapril Hydrochloride loaded microsphere was analyzed by optical microscopy. All the batches of microspheres show uniform size distribution. The average particle size of Quinapril Hydrochloride loaded microspheres was found to be in the range of 235.2 to 412.7 μm . As the stirring rate was increased, the microspheres size was also found to be decreased (table 2).

Scanning Electron Microscopy

The microspheres had good spherical geometry as evidenced by the SEM photographs. The surface of the microspheres was quite smooth (figure1).

In vitro drug release studies

Dissolution studies were carried out using USP II dissolution test apparatus (paddle). Capsule was tied to paddle with a cotton thread so that the capsule was immersed completely in dissolution media but not float. In order to simulate the pH changes along the GI tract, three dissolution media with pH 1.2, 7.4 and 6.8 were sequentially used, (sequential pH change method). The pH 1.2 was first used for 2 hrs then removed and the fresh phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was added. After 4 hrs the medium was removed and colonic fluid phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was added for subsequent study. 900 ml of the dissolution medium was used at each time. Rotation speed was 50 rpm and temperature was maintained at $37\pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$. 10ml of dissolution medium was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals and fresh dissolution media was replaced. The withdrawn samples were analyzed at 210 nm, by UV absorption spectroscopy and the cumulative percentage release was calculated. (Table 3)

Table:1 Various formulations of Pulsatile Microspheres.

Formulation Code	Drug (10mg)	Polymer	Concentration	Solvent	External Phase
F1	10	Ethyl Cellulose	1	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F2	10	Ethyl Cellulose+ Eudragit RS100	1:1	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F3	10	Ethyl Cellulose+ Eudragit RS100	2:1	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F4	10	Ethyl Cellulose+ Eudragit RS100	3:1	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F5	10	Ethyl Cellulose+ Eudragit RS100	4:1	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F6	10	Eudragit RS100	1	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F7	10	Ethyl Cellulose+ Eudragit RS100	1:2	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F8	10	Ethyl Cellulose+ Eudragit RS100	1:3	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA
F9	10	Ethyl Cellulose+ Eudragit RS100	1:4	Dichloromethane	0.4 % PVA

Table. 2 Standard Calibration of Quinapril Hydrochloride.

Sr. No.	Conc. µg/ml	Absorbance		
		pH 1.2	pH 6.8	pH 7.4
1	2	0.04	0.061	0.265
2	4	0.086	0.118	0.526
3	6	0.120	0.162	0.841
4	8	0.172	0.202	0.984
5	10	0.213	0.263	1.295
6	12	0.246	0.301	1.552
7	14	0.350	0.332	1.792

Table:3 Evaluation of Microspheres.

Batch Code	Theoretical Yield (gm)	Practical yield (gm)	%Practical Yield	%Drug loading	Entrapment efficiency	Particle size (µm)
F-1	1	0.47	47%	91.84%	91.84%	235.2
F-2	1	0.82	82%	96.67%	96.67%	261.07
F-3	1.2	1.02	85%	94.31%	94.31%	412.7
F-4	1.2	0.75	62.50%	96.95%	96.95%	245.78
F-5	1	0.93	93.0%	95.04%	95.04%	294
F-6	1	0.932	93.20%	96.00%	96.00%	285.07
F-7	1.2	0.87	72.50%	94.29%	94.29%	261.07
F-8	1.2	0.985	82.03%	92.58%	92.58%	243.43
F-9	1	0.92	92.00%	89.30%	89.30%	262.24

Figure. 1 FTIR of Quinapril Hydrochloride.

Figure. 2 FTIR of optimized batch.

Figure. 3 Standard calibration of Quinapril Hydrochloride.

Figure. 4 SEM of optimized batch.

Table. 4 *In-vitro* drug release of Quinapril Hcl Pulsatile microspheres.

Time	Formulation Batches								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	3.913	4.304	4.304	4.304	4.695	4.304	5.086	4.304	5.869
2	5.086	4.695	5.478	5.086	5.478	5.869	5.869	5.086	7.043
3	5.478	5.478	8.217	6.26	6.26	7.826	7.434	5.478	7.434
4	7.043	10.956	11.739	9.391	7.826	9.782	12.913	10.173	15.26
5	12.521	15.26	17.608	17.608	13.695	17.608	18.782	14.869	22.695
6	20.739	25.434	30.913	19.956	25.434	25.043	32.086	23.086	34.434
7	47.671	40.218	42.82	37.125	37.125	35.859	37.195	42.046	40.078
8	61.312	50.273	53.859	44.437	44.437	48.093	46.265	54.14	55.054
9	67.429	64.687	66.585	69.117	69.117	65.25	69.187	66.726	68.06
10	77.203	75.585	72.984	76.781	76.781	77.765	73.406	72.21	73.757
11	80.859	80.156	77.765	80.929	80.929	80.578	82.265	79.101	77.765
12	85.148	83.25	83.531	84.304	84.304	82.687	84.937	81.632	82.195

CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to explore the feasibility of time dependent pulsatile drug delivery system of Quinapril hydrochloride for the treatment of Hypertension. A satisfactory attempt was made to develop pulsatile system of Quinapril hydrochloride and evaluated it. As per the finding from current research work, it was concluded that Ethyl Cellulose and Eudragit RS100 provide extended drug release to the microspheres. It provides better lag time with limited release of drug during average gastric emptying time. As per the experimental result revealed, formulation F1 was selected as optimized formulations as they were meet the demand of chronobiology of disease. Hence, it can be concluded that pulsatile unit of Quinapril Hydrochloride may be providing a better pharmacological effect, thus can be effectively used in management of hypertension.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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